

A Measurement of the 2022 Budget Allocations on Marketing Performance Across Key Economic Sectors: A Zambian Perspective

Dr. Francis Mukosa
ZCAS University
Lusaka

Mildred Muhyila
ZCAS University
Lusaka

Dr. Burton Mweemba
ZCAS University
Lusaka

Dr. Windu Matoka
ZCAS University
Lusaka

Abstract:- The Ministry of Finance in Zambia announced a 173 billion national budget with an increase of CDF funds. The increase in CDF funds is expected to result into high economic growth and ultimately increase marketing performance across the key economic sectors which are Agriculture, Tourism, Mining and commerce. This research measures the impact of the 2022 resource allocations on the marketing performance in each key economic sector. There has been no measure of the relationship between budgetary allocations and marketing performance across the key economic sectors particularly for the 2022 national budget. The research used a survey with 110 respondents who provided answers to address the research questions. The major finding was that there is a relationship between resource allocation and marketing performance across the economic growth sectors.

Keywords:- Budget, Marketing, Performance, Sector, Growth.

I. INTRODUCTION

Marketing is essential for the organic growth of companies and this is why firms provide huge budgets in billions of dollars to such a function (Gupta & Steenburgh, 2008). The arguments that have always existing in Corporate boards are always associated with justifying Marketing investments but on the other hand metrics exist that allow Marketing investments to be justified. The Marketing function is responsible largely for creating awareness, communication and increasing revenue generation across functional units in firms. At national level Marketing is critical to economic growth as it is the driver for mindset change and economic growth (Sinha, et al., 2013).

The Minister of Finance in Zambia announced a ZMW 173 billion national budget for 2022 with increased allocation for CDF by over 200% (IBDO, 2021). This increase in resource allocation is expected to increase Marketing activities at constituency level particularly for activities in the key economic sectors of mining, agriculture, commerce and tourism. The increase in investments in the key sectors is expected to increase GDP with a projected growth of 3.9% by 2023 (Trading Economics, 2021). This research intends to

measure that impact of these increased allocation on Marketing performance across the key economic growth sectors.

A. Problem Statement

The impact of the increase in sector allocation on Marketing performance across key sectors is not known and requires estimates to be made in order to have a realistic expectation of Marketing performance by 2023 in Zambia. The research aims to measure the 2022 budget allocations on Marketing performance across key economic sectors in Zambia.

B. Objectives

1. To determine the extent to which resource allocations in the 2022 nation budget impact Marketing in Zambia
2. To evaluate the implications of the increase in CDF from 1.6 million to 25.6 million on awareness and communication role in constituencies in Zambia
3. To determine the relationship between Marketing activities and economic growth

C. Hypothesis

➤ Hypothesis 1

H₁: Resource allocations in the 2022 national budget will lead to a high economic growth

H₀: Resource allocations in the 2022 national budget will not lead to a high economic growth

➤ Hypothesis 2

H₁: Increase in CDF from 1.6 million to 25.6 million will result in increase in awareness roles and communications in constituencies

H₀: increase in CDF from 1.6 million to 25.6 million will not result in awareness roles and communication in constituencies

D. Research Question

The research question that was asked to achieve the objectives was; does increase in national budgetary allocations lead to an increase in Marketing performance?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study was compiled by analyzing three main key reports as the literature review and these are the budget speech or reports for 2021 and 2022 as released by the ministry of Finance, the reports on Zambia’s economic outlook by the World bank and the Monetary Policy Committee Statement of the Bank of Zambia. The other documents are the PMRC budget analysis report and the Zambia Parliament yellow books.

III. ZAMBIA’S ECONOMIC OUTLOOK-A LITERATURE REVIEW

The World Bank pronounced that Zambia’s growth rate for 2021 was projected at -2.8 with an inflation rate reported at 15.7% for the same year (World Bank, 2020). While the World Bank was projecting a negative GDP growth for Zambia and almost all the Southern African countries, the Bank of Zambia on the other hand projected an annual GDP growth of 3.7% (Bank of Zambia, 2021). The projection in economic growth by the Bank of Zambia is expected to increased economic activities in the Agriculture sector, retail sector and the information and communication sectors. The projection by the World Bank imply that there would be very little cash movements in the economy with most corporate organizations cutting down Marketing budgets to survive the COVID-19 pandemic which seems to have a more destructive effect on World economies than on the global death toll (Yunfeng , et al., 2021). The comparison of projections by the World Bank are computed in table one below against the projections by the World Bank.

Table 1: Comparisons of Economic indicators					
World Bank Indicators			Bank of Zambia Indicators		
	2021	2022		2021	2022
GDP	2.8%	2.8%	GDP	3.3%	2.0%
Inflation Rate	22.2%	15.7%	Inflation	22.6	15%

Source (Bank of Zambia Monetary policy report and the World Bank Overview Report)

The projections by the World Bank and the Bank of Zambia seem to be pointing in the same direction of economic growth except on inflation which reported an actual increase in 2021 by the Bank of Zambia by 2.8% in the first two quarters of 2021 as key economic industry activities increased. Marketing activities in the country depend very much on the cash flows as projected by the Ministry of Finance since this is what determines the buying power of government ministries and policy support to the key economic sectors. Fiscal deficit on a cash basis was expected to rise by 11.7% of GDP in 2021 (PMRC, 2020). For 2022 PMRC projects Fiscal deficit on a cash basis at around 11.6% to 12.3% citing that contribution from the agriculture sector is unstable with relative declines from 15.6% in 2010 to 2.73% in 2019 (World Bank, 2020).

Crop Marketing is expected to be affected negatively as the sector shrinks and this has an implication on the Marketing sector since revenues decline and funding to Marketing activities reduces.

IV. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig 1: conceptual framework

The assumption in the Framework in Figure 1 is that when allocations to the key economic sectors in the 2022 national budgets increase they will trigger an increase in Marketing activities which will lead to economic growth. Economic growth therefore is the independent variable while Marketing activities form the dependent variable.

V. METHODOLOGY

This research is a survey conducted using a random sampling method to investigate the implications of the 2022 budget allocations on Marketing across key economic sectors in Zambia. The sample size targeted was 100 respondents of which 110 provided responses compiled in the findings discussed in the next section. The response rate was above the data collected by 9% and according to Hair is more than 70% of the targeted data and this means that the sample is highly representative (Hair, et al., 2014).

A. Sampling method

The sampling method was random sampling, the researcher opted to use random sampling in order to get views that were unbiased. During the data collection process the researcher distributed a structured questionnaire with closed ended questions generated through a Google form link.

B. Comparisons of revenue allocation to the key economic sectors

Table 2: Comparisons of sector allocation 2021 to 2022				
	Mining	Agriculture	Tourism	Commerce
2021	78.4%	40.2%	7.2%	26.1%
2022	77.1%	40.6%	7.7%	27.4%

Table 2 shows estimated contributions in terms of revenue for the key economic sectors in Zambia. From analyzing details in Table 2 there is a projection of increment in sector allocations in each key sector, 2021 was mainly a recovery year from the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic (Osakwe, 2022). The increase in the revenue allocations is expected to give a rise to Marketing activities in each key sector. However, these assertions can only be verified through conducting some scientific measurements from a number of responses by respondents in the selected sample.

C. Data reliability test

Data quality tests are important because they improve or validate the data to generate research interest and they also determine the extent to which it is consistent across the sample (Rothmans, 2007). The researcher adopted the Cronbach Alpha test using SPSS scale reliability analysis, according to Taber a Cronbach Alpha test that is above 0.70 implies a high data reliability (Taber, 2017) .

Table 3: Case Processing Summary

	N	%
Valid	105	95.5
Cases Excluded	5	4.5
Total	110	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 3 above shows the case processing in SPSS at 95% with 5 excluded items, the 5 items are 4% of the total items and since it is less than 10% it may not affect the outcome of the analysis of data (Koonce & Kelly, 2014).

Cronbach Alpha is defined as a measure used to assess the internal consistency of test items. If the measure of the test is between 60% to 70% then the data is acceptable but if the data is above 70% then it is high (Goforth, 2015).

Table 4: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.808	18

Table 4 shows that the reliability test was .808 which interprets into 80% reliability of all the 18 items tested. The structured questionnaire feed into SPSS had 18 sets of questions and this means that all question was tested with 105 listwise and 5 excluded.

D. Ministry of Finance projections

The address by the minister of Finance Honorable Situmbeko Musokotwane in parliament projected economic growth for 2022 at 5.9% (Musokotwane, October, 2021). The projection is higher than those by both the Bank of Zambia and the World Bank by 3.9% and 3.1% respectively and if this

becomes a reality sectors such as the Tourism sector that is heavily dependent on Marketing is poised to record growth. The Tourism sector has been allocated an estimated 117 million Kwacha for 2022, a reduction by almost 11% (Zambia Yellow Books, 2022). The reduction in the allocation means that the sector will reduce its promotional campaign budgets and ultimately budgets for Marketing. COVID-19 affected this sector negatively in 2020 implying that recovery is important for 2022 through aggressive Marketing by the Zambia National Tourism Board (ZNTB).

VI. DATA FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

E. Gender of respondents

The researcher wanted to identify the gender of the respondents in order to fully understand the dynamics of the responses from the sample, understanding the gender of respondents is important in any research for strategy, communication and decision making (Tannenbaum, et al., 2016).

Table 5: Select your gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	28	25.5	25.5	25.5
Valid Male	82	74.5	74.5	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 shows that Female respondents were less than male respondents by 50% implying that there was more participation from males than females in the survey. The females consisted of 25% of total respondents while the males consisted of 74.5%. Table 5 also shows that all 110 respondents answered the question of what is their gender.

F. Tax Payer status of respondents

This demographic was important as the research bordered on budget analysis and allocations to key economic sectors. Tax payers in any governance system are the authority in decision making. Tax payers form the intrinsic aspects of Tax morale in a governance system and this means that Tax payers are paramount in decision making (Sebele-Mpofu, 2020). Understanding whether someone is a tax payer or not in this research was important in order to get views from respondents with a real concern for government budgetary allocations.

Table 6: Are you a tax payer?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	6	5.5	5.5	5.5
Valid Yes	104	94.5	94.5	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

Table 6 shows that 94.5% of respondents were tax payers while 5.5% were not, this finding means that the majority of respondents fall into the bracket of individuals with a voice on national budget allocation.

Table 7: The 2022 Budget presented by the Minister of Finance has adequate answers to economic growth

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	1	.9	.9	.9
Disagree	6	5.5	5.5	6.4
Neutral	23	20.9	20.9	27.3
Agree	53	48.2	48.2	75.5
Strongly Agree	27	24.5	24.5	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

Table 7 indicates the responses were skewed towards respondents suggesting that the 2022 budget had adequate answers to economic growth. From Table 7, 24.5% of respondents strongly agreed while 48.2% agreed that the 2022 budget had adequate answers to economic growth. From the findings only 9% strongly disagreed while 6% disagreed with 27.3% remaining neutral. The graph in Figure 2 below provides evidence that the data was skewed towards the 2022 budget having adequate answers to Zambia’s economic growth.

Fig 2: Adequacy of the 2022 National budget to economic growth

Figure 2 also shows that the data was leptokurtic, the negative skewness in Table 8 confirms that respondents thought that the 2022 National budget.

Table 8: Statistics on adequacy of Budget on economic growth

The 2022 Budget presented by the Minister of Finance has adequate answers to economic growth

N	Valid	110
	Missing	0
Mean		3.90
Median		4.00
Mode		4
Std. Deviation		.867
Skewness		-.665
Std. Error of Skewness		.230
Kurtosis		.411
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.457

The Kurtosis in table 8 is .457, this means that the data is fairly symmetrical but the skewness shows a negative value confirming the results of the histogram in Figure 1. In addition, the mean is also less than 5 and this means that the data is skewed towards the 2022 National budget providing adequate answers to economic growth. Kolapo & Adaramola (2012) linked economic growth to Marketing performance in Nigeria by studying the performance of economic markets and allocations to Marketing sectors, which seemed to go up each time stocks went up (Kolapo & Adaramola, 2012).

The findings by Kolapo & Adaramola (2012) in Nigeria form an interesting basis for comparing findings with the ones in this survey. Table 9 shows that that 41.8% of respondents agreed that Economic growth in Zambia depends largely on Marketing, with 34% strongly agreeing, 12% remained neutral with 2.7% strongly disagreeing while 8.2% disagreed.

Table 9: Economic growth in Zambia depends largely on Marketing activities

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	3	2.7	2.7	2.7
Disagree	9	8.2	8.2	10.9
Neutral	14	12.7	12.7	23.6
Agree	46	41.8	41.8	65.5
Strongly Agree	38	34.5	34.5	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

Table 9 leads to an assertion that the findings were skewed towards respondents agreeing that economic development is largely dependent on Marketing activities. Figure 3 shows that the data collected from the sample was skewed towards respondents stating that economic growth is highly dependent on Marketing activities. Zambia has begun

a shift from dependency on mining to agriculture, since 1990 Marketing agricultural subsidies has increased from 56 Million kwacha in 1975 to 3 billion kwacha (Chiwele, et al., 1996).

Figure 3: Dependency of Economic growth on Marketing

To support the findings in Figure 3 Table 10 shows that the skewness is between -1 and 0.5 and this means that negatively skewed towards the assumption that economic growth in Zambia depends largely on Marketing activities.

Table 10: Statistics on Dependency of Economic Growth on Marketing

Economic growth in Zambia depends largely on Marketing activities

N	Valid	110
	Missing	0
Mean		3.97
Median		4.00
Skewness		-1.032
Std. Error of Skewness		.230
Kurtosis		.626
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.457

The Zambian government pronounced an increase in CDF of 94% in the 2022 budget with a view to improve awareness and development at constituency level (Zambia Yellow Books, 2022). The increase in CDF is expected to boost Marketing activities in the key economic sectors. Table 11 shows 51.8% of respondents indicated that they strongly agreed that the increase in CDF implies more communication and awareness in roles within constituencies.

Table 11: Increase in CDF from ZMK 1.6 Million to ZMK 25.7 Million implies more communication and awareness roles within constituencies

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	1	.9	.9	.9
Disagree	5	4.5	4.5	5.5
Neutral	14	12.7	12.7	18.2
Agree	33	30.0	30.0	48.2
Strongly Agree	57	51.8	51.8	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

The findings in Table 11 also show that 30% of respondents agreed that CDF increase would result in more communication and awareness roles within constituencies while 4.5% disagreed while only 0.9% disagreed. Figure 4 shows that the responses were skewed towards respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing that increase in CDF will result into increase in awareness and communication in constituencies.

Fig 4: Increase in CDF leading to increase in awareness and communication roles

The skewness of the data is confirmed by the findings in Table 12 below which shows a skewness of -1 confirming that the data is negatively skewed to support the assumption that increase in CDF allocation will result into increase in awareness and communication.

Table 12: Statistics on CDF increase

Increase in CDF from ZMK 1.6 Million to ZMK 25.7 Million implies more communication and awareness roles in constituencies

N	Valid	110
	Missing	0
Mean		4.27
Median		5.00
Skewness		-1.225
Std. Error of Skewness		.230
Kurtosis		1.027
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.457

While the government has increased CDF to constituencies, expectations is that communication and awareness become paramount to implementation of developmental projects across key sectors. This means that Marketing is key to attaining economic growth across the key sectors; Agriculture, Tourism, Mining and Commerce. Respondents in Table 13 felt that Marketing is key in growing the economic sectors.

Table 13 Marketing in sectors such as Tourism, Agriculture, Mining and Commerce is critical to attaining growth

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	1	.9	.9	.9
Disagree	1	.9	.9	1.8
Valid Agree	25	22.7	22.7	24.5
Strongly Agree	83	75.5	75.5	100.0
Total	110	100.0	100.0	

The findings in Table 13 show a clear inclination to the assertion that Marketing in sectors such as Tourism, Agriculture, Mining and Commerce are critical to attaining growth. In Table 13, 75% of respondent strongly agreed that Marketing was critical in attaining growth in the key sectors while 22.7% agreed to the same with only 0.9% disagreed and agreed respectively.

Figure 5 shows a negatively skewed graph confirming the findings in Table 13, with increase in CDF Marketing activities are expected to increase.

Fig 5: Marketing in sectors such as Tourism, Agriculture, Mining and Commerce is critical to attaining growth

The findings in Table 4 are confirmed by the skewness and Kurtosis tests in Table 14 below showing a skewness of -3 implying that Marketing is key in growth across the four key economic sectors.

Table 14: Statistics on Key Sectors

Marketing in sectors such as Tourism, Agriculture, Mining and Commerce is critical to attaining growth

N	Valid	110
	Missing	0
Mean		4.71
Median		5.00
Skewness		-3.186
Std. Error of Skewness		.230
Kurtosis		14.308
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.457

Table 15: Hypothesis test Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The categories of Increase in CDF from ZMK 1.6 Million to ZMK 25.7 Million implies more communication and awareness roles in constituencies occur with equal probabilities.	One-Sample Chi-Square Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
2	The categories of Marketing in sectors such as Tourism, Agriculture, Mining and Health is critical to attaining growth occur with equal probabilities.	One-Sample Chi-Square Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
3	The categories of Ecomic growth in Zambia depends largely on marketing activities occur with equal probabilities.	One-Sample Chi-Square Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

➤ *Non-parametric test result with Chi square*

The hypothesis test summaries in Figure 5 show a rejection in the Null hypothesis, with a significance value of 0.00 confirming the results of the correlation results in Table 15.

The Null hypothesis on each of the chosen items has been rejected to agree on the alternate hypothesis. This implies that the respondents were of the view that increase in CDF can lead to an increase in communication and awareness roles in constituencies and that budget allocations for 2022 can lead to economic growth. The Anova test in Table 16 below shows the results of the Anova test.

Table 16: One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Increase in CDF from ZMK 1.6 Million to ZMK 25.7 Million implies more communication and awareness roles in constituencies	48.826	109	.000	4.273	4.10	4.45
Economic growth in Zambia depends largely on Marketing activities	40.579	109	.000	3.973	3.78	4.17
Marketing in sectors such as Tourism, Agriculture, Mining and Commerce is critical to attaining growth	80.835	109	.000	4.709	4.59	4.82

The significance in the Anova test in Table 16 is 0.00 confirming the strong relationships among the variables and also implying that the increase in resource allocations increases Marketing performance. The DF value is also very high at 109 < 27 and this means that the variable relationship is very significant confirming the Null hypothesis rejection. The test value is 0 and the interval confidence level is 95% implying a high significance in the assertion that increase in budgetary allocations across the key sectors will result in an increase in Marketing performance. A P value of .00 implies that there are significant relationships among the variables tested and in Table 16 the P value for all the relationships was < 0 with a DF of 109 confirming the strong relationships among the variables tested (University of New England, 2000).

VII. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Research objective 1 (RO1) was framed as; To determine the extent to which resource allocations in the 2022 nation budget impact Marketing in Zambia. From the analysis in Table 11 respondent stated that increase in CDF would result in increased communication and awareness activities at constituency level. According to Batra & Keller (2016), integrated Marketing communication forms an important aspect of Marketing and when there is an increase in awareness and communication, Marketing activities increase (Batra & Keller, 2016). This means that the findings in Table 11 have addressed RO1. Findings in Table 9 further provide answers to address RO1, in that 34.5% strongly agreed that Marketing activities are key to economic growth with only 2.7% of respondents strongly disagreed. The findings in Table 9 are supported by findings by Peter Drucker who stated in his findings that Marketing is also the most effective engine of economic development since it impresses its ability in entrepreneur and manager development (Drucker, 1958).

RO2 was framed as: To evaluate the implications of the increase in CDF from 1.6 million to 25.6 million. Clearly the findings in Table 11 confirm that the increase in CDF from 1.6 Million to 25.7 million will result in increase in Marketing activities, the results of the Anova test in Table 16 also show that the significance between the two variables in RO1 and RO2 is 0.00 further confirming that findings for both objectives are fully addressed. Lindgren & Lindgren in their research indicated that Marketing is essential in development of a community, city or nation, further supporting the findings in this research (Lindgren & Lindgren, 2011).

RO3 was phrased as; To determine the relationship between Marketing activities and economic growth. Research findings in Table 15 show that there is a strong correlation between the question of increase in CDF and economic growth, this is empirical evidence that there is a very strong relationship between increase in resource allocation and economic growth. Table 15 further shows a strong relationship between increased awareness and communication in constituencies and economic growth. A research conducted by Allen et al who investigated the role of Marketing in economic development in Africa-Tanzania found that Marketing had an impact on people on people since it has the ability to change behaviors (Allen, et al., 2017). The findings by Allen et al are a strong confirmation that purely there is a relationship between Marketing and national economic growth.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This research brought out findings that there is a relationship between resource allocation and Marketing performance. The increase in resource allocation in CDF from 1.6 Million to 25.7 Million is expected to give increase in Marketing activities since awareness and communication activities are expected to take center stage. Crop Marketing is a huge component in the performance of the agriculture sector in Zambia, conversely sectors such as the retail sector and Tourism are fully dependent on Marketing. Marketing cuts across all the four key sectors of economic development in

Zambia and the implication of this is that it must be regarded as a strategic partner to national economic development. The relationship between budgetary allocation and Marketing performance has been established in this research and well supported by findings from other research by Drucker and Allen.

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